

**THEORETICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF
METHODS OF TEACHING CHESS TO
SCHOOLCHILDREN**

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Annotation: The article presents an analysis of the main provisions of gaming activities, and develops directions for research into combining the mental and physical education of students. The work shows the influence of play on a child's development and substantiates the expansion of the concept of "thinking".

Key words: chess, schoolchildren, active sports, physical education, intellectual education.

Introduction. The study of the influence of the educational process on the harmonious development of students in secondary general education institutions is a relevant problem in the era of increasing demands for fundamental changes in educational technologies, increasing information load, reducing the objective need to achieve a high level of physical fitness for existence in the modern social environment [3, 5]. In the conditions of this study, the unity of consciousness and activity through the knowledge of internal, mental phenomena in accordance with their external detection in actions, behavior, speech, movements, gestures and other reactions turns out to be the leading principle of approaching the objectivity of scientific research [1, 2, 4]. Among the tasks of mental education, experts include the process of forming in students a correct idea of learning as a complex process associated with constant exertion of will, the need to overcome difficulties, and produce such positive qualities as hard work, discipline, high consciousness, and a responsible attitude to work [3, 6, 8]. The main objectives of physical education, according to the authors of scientific and pedagogical literature, are to promote the

physical development of a person, develop a positive influence on the consolidation of moral and strong-willed character traits, develop such personality qualities as organization, conscious discipline, perseverance in the process of overcoming obstacles [3, 7, 9].

N. N. Norbojev notes that learning is fun and enjoyable if it is creative, skillfully managed by the teacher and self-managed by the student [10,11, 14]. These aspects, according to our observations, find their practical manifestation through the inclusion in the educational and training process of the development of children's motor abilities, tasks of the formative processes of learning to play chess. At the initiative of UNESCO, special commissions observed several groups of children who had previously been identified as having the same level of intellectual development. The standard school curriculum for the experimental group additionally included chess lessons. After testing, the speed of intellectual response in the experimental group was found to be an order of magnitude higher than in the control group, in which children were taught according to the traditional program [12, 13]. Analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature indicates that the subject of scientific research by scientists was the formation of students' needs for physical education and self-improvement, the self-awareness of the individual, his motives, attitudes, and value orientations. Based on the analysis of pedagogical, psychological literature, literature on physical education and sports, we are inclined to note that the problem of mental and physical development of students in general education institutions is widely covered by the authors. But the problems of studying theoretical and methodological issues of studying the mutual influence of the dynamics of the development of children's mental and physical abilities through the means of including learning to play chess in the organization of outdoor games are not covered in the scientific and pedagogical literature. In the study of the processes of mutual influence of mental and motor activity of students and the theoretical and methodological justification of pedagogical technologies for the effectiveness of the

teaching and educational process, the novelty and relevance of this research is revealed.

N. N. Norboev notes that “personality is formed in the conditions of a person’s concrete historical existence, in activity [3]. Experts argue that “human activity is characterized by consciousness and purposefulness” [4]. In satisfying his needs, a person interacts with the environment, forms his goals and, under the influence of motives, chooses the means of achieving them, showing physical and mental activity. “The conscious nature of human activity is manifested in its planning, prediction of results, regulation of actions, and the desire to improve it” [7].

Maksimenko defines human activity as “conscious activity manifested in a system of actions aimed at achieving a set goal.” The author sees genetic connections with the organic and cultural needs of the individual in the motives of human activity and behavior. And needs, which, according to the scientist, can be motivated to activity, are classified into material (needs for clothing, food, housing) and spiritual and cultural (cognitive, socio-political, aesthetic). Taking into account the purpose, content and forms, S. D. Maksimenko generalizes the classification of activities into: play, learning and work. The author considers play activity to be the main means of a child’s cognition of the outside world, reflecting it in the form of sensations, perceptions, ideas, which creates the main form of identifying the child’s activity. In psychology, it is believed that “games not only reveal, but also form all the mental processes and properties of children, observation, attentiveness, thoughtfulness, perseverance, courage, determination, ability, skills, abilities. In play activities, not only mental, but also physical development of children occurs, physical strength, dexterity, speed and accuracy of movements develop” [9].

Specialists in the theory and methodology of physical education and sports have widely covered the principles, forms, means and methods of organizing sports and outdoor games, their educational and training significance. O. V. Timoshenko, R. M. Misharovskiy and V. Ya. Makhov note that “outdoor games are characterized by the activity and independence of the players, collectivism of actions and

continuous changes in the conditions of activity. The actions of the players are subject to certain rules that regulate their behavior and relationships, facilitating the choice of tactics and management of the game.” The authors note that “The basis of outdoor games is active creative motor actions, motivated by a plot (theme, idea), partially limited by rules” [9]. From the point of view of classification of games, experts distinguish three main groups: creative games, outdoor games and sports [6]. Considering this classification, in our vision, the game of chess can be classified as creative and sports games (in the context of the use of competition), and the inclusion of teaching chess in the organization of outdoor games should enrich the motivational and cognitive components of attracting children to active and harmonious development. enrich the motor formation of such activity.

S. B. Gubnitsky, M. G. Khanukov, S. A. Shedei emphasize that play is an integral form of activity; play is necessary for children as a means of satisfying the organic need for self-expression and modeling social relationships [1, 8]. The authors note that in chess, not only the result is important, but also the interest in the process of the game as a path illuminated by the desire to win. This path has educational significance through movement in achieving set goals, the emergence of plans, anticipation of dangerous situations, and responsibility for the risk of independent decision-making [14].

Chess instills self-control in children, developing the ability to concentrate and control their actions. Experts emphasize that chess develops thinking that is neutral in relation to good and evil; it acts as a moral lesson in fair sports competition. V. E. Zherebkin calls thinking a property of matter, which does not exist separately, but is a function of the human brain. The author defines thinking as indirect sensory cognition, arising on the basis of sensations as the processing of sensory material. The scientist emphasizes that thinking reflects not only the properties directly given in sensations and perceptions, but also such signs, aspects, connections of objects that are manifested directly by the mind. M. G. Torful notes that “thinking as a complex phenomenon is the subject of study of many sciences - epistemology,

psychology, cybernetics, linguistics”. The author reveals the essence of the main scientific directions in the study of human thinking:

- 1) “epistemology explores the relationship of thinking to being, its emergence and development, the relationship with the sensory degree of knowledge, the problem of truth”;
- 2) “psychology studies thinking regarding those causes and conditions that ensure the normal functioning and development of thinking in the individual development of a person, the influence of emotions, will and other mental phenomena on thinking”;
- 3) “cybernetics studies thinking by modeling it in the form of special schemes through which the perception, memorization and processing of information is carried out for the purpose of its effective transmission”;
- 4) “the physiology of higher nervous activity studies thinking from the side of material processes occurring in the cells of the cerebral cortex (neurons) and constituting its physiological basis”.

Psychologists define thinking as “the process of indirect and generalized human cognition of objects and phenomena of objective reality in their essential properties, connections and relationships.” As V. E. Zherebkin notes: “Thinking takes the general, essential from objects and phenomena and separates (abstracts) from the secondary, unimportant. Compared to perception and representation, thinking allows us to understand the objective world more deeply and completely, to reveal the most important, most significant aspects, connections and patterns of reality”. N. N. Norboyev emphasizes that “by thinking, a person cognizes what he cannot directly perceive and imagine; comes to an understanding of the essence of the phenomena of the world, forms a concept about them and practically masters them”.

Conclusions. Thus, taking into account the relevance of the inclusion of gaming activities in the educational process, the use of all its classification characteristics, indicated by the author of professional literature, noting the

properties of the influence of gaming activities on the harmonious and creative development of children, we are inclined to note that the use of technologies for combining the development of mental and physical activity of children is a pressing issue of innovation of pedagogical impact. This expands the range of research areas:

- 1) in the study of the formative processes of students' logical thinking;
- 2) in the study of the influence of physical activity on the characteristics and characteristics of thinking;
- 3) in the study of the influence of thinking processes on the tactical preparedness of athletes;
- 4) in the study of psychological aspects of thinking processes and the psychology of sports training.

Such areas of research problems, in our vision, can be solved by including educational processes in the development of skills in playing chess in the gaming motor activity of students.

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